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Evaluation of a Landrace Potato Kumdi Performance and Attributed Traits across Three Different Agro-Ecological Zones in the Highlands of Papua New Guinea

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Abstract

This study was conducted to assess attributed traits and economic performances of the landrace Kumdi potato cultivar in comparison to the existing commercial varieties at three different agro-environments in the highlands of Papua New Guinea. Several field trials were conducted over two cropping seasons using a complete randomized block design with five replicates. The landrace Kumdi and the two released varieties (E2 and E24) were found to be highly resistant (90 – 100%) to potato late blight (PLB) disease, whereas Sequoia is known to be highly susceptible and was successfully controlled with fungicide applications across all sites. The results indicated significant variation for the Genotypes, Environments and Genotype by Environment interactions. The marketable and total yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$) for Sequoia was higher than the yields of the other three genotypes across all sites. Kumdi appeared to be the most stable cultivar across the three environments by using various stability analysis parameters. The fresh boiled and fried chips consumer preferences for Kumdi and Sequoia were highly prepared followed by E2 and E24, but the consumers' preferences for all these varieties were above 50% like to compare to the moderately like and dislike preferences. Profit margins varied across locations with Kumdi having a greater profit margin for Yawar while E2 and E24 showed a greater profit margin for Pepik and Aiyura respectively while Sequoia had the highest production cost due to PLB management. Overall, Kumdi had acceptable traits of being resistant to PLB infestation, are most stable across all tested environments, and had acceptable profit margins with highly preferred sensory preferences. Based on these findings, the landrace Kumdi cultivar is strongly recommended for further research to verify these results using clean planting materials and possibly be included in the formal seed system.

Key words: *Potato varieties, potato late blight, consumer preference and cost benefit analysis*

INTRODUCTION

The Irish potato (*Solanum tuberosum L.*) is an important crop, widely grown both for food and cash income by smallholder farmers in high altitude (elevation of 1600-2800m above sea level) farming communities in Papua New Guinea (PNG) (Sawanga, 1991 and FAO, 2009). The production of potato for formal trade in the country is undertaken largely by smallholder farmers with a farm size of less than a hectare (0.1- 0.5 ha). In 2013 the production was estimated to be approximately 18,000 tons per annum valued at PGK 16-18 million (FPDA Annual Report, 2013). This was earned by trading in urban centers for fresh consumption, chips in fast food outlets and restaurants and trading into catering companies (Anton *et al.*, 2018; Bourke *et al.*, 2001).

In PNG, the infestation of potato late blight (PLB) disease caused by the fungus *Phytophthora infestans* led to a considerable reduction in potato production in the highlands of PNG in 2003, particularly for the most commonly grown and highly susceptible commercial variety, Sequoia (Minemba and Kerru, 2014). As a result

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of PLB infestation, Sequoia could only be grown with high input of fungicides, Eko 720 (active ingredient, 720g L⁻¹ Chlorothalonil) not only increasing production cost, but also posing risks to the health of producers (Rani *et al.*, 2017) and moving potato production out of reach especially for subsistence farmers. The use of disease-resistant plant varieties is a more sustainable option for smallholder farmers (Kromann *et al.*, 2014) and as a response, the National Agricultural Research Institute (NARI) released a total of four PLB resistant varieties (E2, E24, E11 and E20) originating from the International Potato Centre (CIP) breeding program in 2011 and 2013 that are producing yields equivalent to Sequoia but with no or much less use of fungicides after an extensive evaluation program (Kerru and Akanda, 2011; Minemba and Kerru, 2014).

At the time the evaluation of the CIP breeding lines was conducted, the NARI team and collaborating partners from the Fresh Produce Development Agency (FPDA) became aware of a landrace cultivar referred to as “Kumdi” named after the Kumdi tribe in the Mul Baiyer District of Western Highlands Province (WHP). The origin of this cultivar is unclear, but it is assumed to have come from earlier introductions during the 1960s/1970s. Kumdi displayed high levels of resistance to PLB and was promoted by local growers.

Since then, Kumdi has become quite popular among growers, especially in the upper highlands region (WHP). However, there is limited knowledge and information available for Kumdi on the adaptability, agronomic performance and level of resistance to PLB across different environments in comparison to the NARI released PLB resistant varieties and Sequoia. Therefore, the aim of this study was to assess the yield performance, stability, level of resistance to PLB fungus and economic potential of Kumdi across three different environments in comparison to the two popular NARI released varieties and the highly PLB susceptible variety Sequoia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sites descriptions and growing seasons

The study was carried out over two consecutive growing seasons between January and September of 2018. Season one was from January to May and Season two was from May to September at three locations in three different highlands provinces. A description of the agro-climatic characteristics of the three trial locations are; Yawar (Tambul in WHP), Pepik (Jiwaka Province) and Aiyura (Eastern Highlands Province) shown in Table 1. The rainfall, altitude and soils information for Yawar, Pepik and Aiyura were obtained during the trial implementation and temperature information was extracted from the National Weather Focus (2018). Characteristics of the four potato varieties used in the study are presented in Table 2.

Table 1: Agro-climatic characteristics of the three trial site

Site	Altitude (masl)	Trial period total Rainfall (mm)	Temperature (°C)	Soil type
Yawar (Tambul)	2212	1588	18 - 22	Volcanic ash soil
Pepik (Jiwaka)	1562	1321	20 - 25	Sandy loam soil
Aiyura (EHP)	1686	1453	24 - 27	Sandy loam soil

Table 2: Characteristics of the four potato cultivars and their origin

Cultivar	Origin	Leaf and flower image	Stem height (cm)	Tuber flesh Colour	Tuber shape	Eye depth	Tuber image

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E2 (NP 01)	CIP						
E24 (NP 02)	CIP						
Kumdi	Unknown						
Sequoia	USA						

Experimental design and planting materials

The experiment was laid out as a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with five replications. The four varieties of potato were randomly assigned to each replicate in a randomized manner. A total of 230m² land areas was prepared manually by hand using spade for each site per season and the treatment plot measured 11.5m² having 36 sample plants per variety. The plant spacing was 80cm by 40cm within rows and between plants respectively. Generation 3 (G3) seed potatoes of varieties E2 (NP01), E24 (NP02) and Sequoia were obtained from FPDA while generation 9 (G9) of Kumdi cultivar was obtained from a local farmer in Tambul. NPK potato mix fertilizer (10:25:12) was basically applied at a rate of 1,200kg ha⁻¹ at the time of planting. Karate (active ingredient, 25 g/L Lambda) was applied at the rate of 2ml L⁻¹ to prevent insect damage from Cutworms (*Agrotis spp.*), Aphids (*Aphidae*) and Planthoppers (*Delphacidae*) at the initial development stage. The fungicide Eko 720 (active ingredient, 720g L⁻¹ Chlorothalonil) was applied only to the Sequoia variety at 1.5ml L⁻¹ at an application frequency of three times a week until the maturity stage. This was done because Sequoia is highly susceptible (Kerru and Akanda, 2011; Minemba and Kerru, 2014) and that measurements of other parameters were needed for the comparisons against the other varieties. Manual hilling, weeding and other cultural practices were done as per standard growing practice (Minemba and Kerru, 2014).

Data collection

PLB and tuber yield assessment

PLB disease severity was assessed using a blight rating system (rating scores 1 – 5 scale): 1 = 20% infestation, 2 = 40% infestation, 3 = 60% infestation, 4 = 80% infestation and 5 = 100% infestation. Five data plants for each treatment were selected and data were collected every three weeks intervals across all sites throughout the experimental periods. At harvest, tuber yield for each variety was recorded as tuber number per plant and total tuber weight (g) per plant in the following categories according to Minemba and Kerru (2014) reports; marketable (>100 grams), seed (10 – 99 grams) and damaged. Tuber weight was converted to tons ha⁻¹ for analysis. For the purpose of the selection, the marketable and total tuber yield component was used for the GxE analysis to compare and select performing varieties for specific and broader adaptation to the environments.

Eating quality assessment

The tubers of the four potato varieties were cured for five days. Eating quality assessment was conducted at Pepik and Tambul NARI station with 30 participants invited from the local community in Pepik and 30 participants from the NARI community. The tubers were peeled and boiled for 25-30 minutes without adding any ingredients using a gas stove burner. Potato chips were prepared by peeling, slicing into 3.4cm long by 0.8-1cm² surfaces, washing, drying and deep-frying with vegetable cooking oil for 20-25 minutes. Assessments were done on flesh colour, aroma, taste and overall qualities by answering “like”, “moderately like” or “dislike” and recorded on the eating quality assessment form. Participants were asked to rinse their mouth with cold water after tasting each potato variety sample to ensure that taste from the previous sample is not carried over to the next sample.

Economics of the Potato

Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) was calculated using the formula:

Net benefit (Profit) = Gross field benefit – Total variable cost

The gross field benefit was calculated from marketable and seed tuber yield ha⁻¹ and the information on the following cost categories was collected for variable cost:

1. Purchases of potato seeds or planting materials.
2. Purchases of fertilizer (NPK Potato Mix).
3. Labor: (land preparation, planting, spraying, hilling and weeding, harvesting and transporting).
4. Purchases of fungicide (Eko 720).
5. Purchases of insecticides (Karate).

The field benefit was adjusted by 5% for seed and marketable yield from the total field benefits. Field benefit for marketable yield was calculated at K1.50/kg (current local farm gate price at Tambul) and seed yield was calculated at K1.80/kg (minimum price). The gross field benefit was calculated by adding seed and marketable field benefits.

Statistical analysis

A combined analysis of variance (ANOVA) was done on marketable and total tuber yield (t ha⁻¹) of four potato varieties evaluated across three different environments using the GenStat 20th edition (Baird et al., 2019) statistical software and R package metan (Olivoto & Lúcio, 2020). Before the analysis of the data, data quality checks were performed using the Shapiro-Wilk test. The ANOVA was done and pooled over locations and using the Generalized Linear Model (GLM) procedures. Since the pooled ANOVA considers only the main effects, the additive main effects and multiplicative interaction model (AMMI) were used to analyze the marketable and total tuber yield (Wera et al., 2018; Funga et al., 2017).

Several AMMI models were used to analyze the stability of Kumdi cultivar and other three varieties evaluated across three environments: *AMMI stability value (ASV)* equation described by Zali et al., (2012) and Gauch, (1992) was used for calculating the stability of the four genotypes evaluated. The *Yield stability index (YSI)* was used to determine the genotype's adaptability by combining both yield and stability in the location using the following formula: **YSI = RASV + RY** as describe by Wera et al., (2018). To further confirm the results from ASV and YSI, the *AMMI biplot* was used to graphically visualized genotype and environments against their respective means, where the abscissa shows the main effects while the ordinates show IPCA1.

The marketable and total tuber yields (t ha⁻¹) of four genotypes primary data were analyzed using the AMMI and presented in the report while the seeds and damaged tuber yields were excluded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION***Potato late blight assessment***

The four potato genotypes (Kumdi, E2, E24 and Sequoia) evaluated across three agro-ecological environments responded differently to PLB pathogen infestation (Figure 1A, 1B and 1C). The trial included treatment of Sequoia without spray which would be the indicator for the presence of the disease pressure but it was not included in the analysis. As expected from previous studies, Sequoia without fungicide application was affected

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at the initial development stage at 21 days after planting (DAP) and exponentially reached 100% severity at 63 DAP to 84 DAP in all sites (Minemba and Kerru, 2014 and Anton *et al.*, 2018). In comparison, infection rates were reduced to below 20% with the application of Chlorothalonil (Eko 720) three times a week on Sequoia (treated) treatment. The high levels of PLB resistance (90 – 100%) shown in earlier evaluation trials for E2 and E24 were confirmed in this trial and also Kumdi displayed 95 – 100% resistance to PLB across all sites (Anton *et al.*, 2018). A very few presence of PLB infections on E2 and Kumdi at Yawar is likely due to higher rainfall during the trial period compared to the two other sites (Table 1). Tambul area receives regular rainfall throughout the year compared to the two other sites (www.worldweatheronline.com). The fact that E2 developed up to 15% infection levels at Yawar is not uncommon. Both varieties E2 and E24 originated from a CIP breeding program aimed at developing potato varieties that have quantitative field resistance. Varieties with this type of resistance show some level of infection depending on the environmental conditions but not resulting in significant yield losses. But it is considered a more durable type of resistance that is not easily overcome by the pathogen (Zadoks & Schein, 1979). The origin and hence, the nature of inheritance of the resistance trait in Kumdi is however unknown. In many of the earlier potato varieties, resistance to PLB was conferred through single resistance genes and changes in the pathogen population resulted in a complete breakdown of the resistance (Forbes, 2012). The higher infection rates observed on all varieties including the resistant CIP clones at Yawar is attributed to the very high rainfalls recorded during the trial period (Table 1). This observation seems consistent with Tjosvold (2018), who stated that the disease infection rate is high when the environment is favourable, the variety is susceptible and the pathogen is virulent. This observation can be tested again by mimicking the high rainfall at a suitable location while subjecting the resistant varieties under high disease pressure.

Kumdi cultivar needs to be closely monitored for its response to PLB fungus under different climatic conditions and locations to justify further studies to gain a better understanding of the type of resistance conferred by Kumdi against PLB fungus.

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Figure 1: PLB infection rate on four potato treatments at 21 – 84 DAP at Yawar (A), Pepik (B) and Aiyura (C) agro-ecological sites.**AMMI ANOVA for marketable and total tuber yield**

Results from the combined analysis of variance (ANOVA) for marketable and total tuber yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$) of four potato genotypes tested in three environments showed highly significant differences ($P < 0.05$) for the environment (E), genotype (G) and the environment by genotype interaction (GEI) (Table 3). Total variations explained were; 49.7% for E, 17.1% for G and 9.2% for GEI for marketable tuber yield and 41.7% for E, 18.7% for G and 8.9% for GEI for total tuber yield. The high percentage of variation attributed to E implies that the environments were diverse, resulting in the large differences among environmental means causing most of the variation in the tuber yield (Funga *et al.*, 2017; Ngeve, 1993). Higher environmental variation in tuber yield traits could be related to very diverse test locations representing the three major agro-ecological zones in the highlands of PNG with differences in terms of altitude, soil type, rainfall and moisture conditions (Table 1). Similarly, genotype showed significant differences ($P < 0.05$) which indicates that four potato genotypes behave differently in each environment and there was a change in the yield components due to the environmental variation. Similar results were reported in the potato GxE study by Byarugaba *et al.* (2018) and Bonierbale (2007). Several authors reported that various crops showed a significant and greater percentage of GxE interaction was explained by the first IPCA score. The results from this study also confirmed that there are significant interactions from GxE in marketable and total tuber yield.

Table 3: ANOVA for Additive Main effects and Multiplicative Interactions (AMMI) of marketable and total tuber yield (t/ha) of 4 genotypes evaluated in 3 locations.

Sources of Variation	D.F.	Marketable Yield (t/ha)				Total Yield (t/ha)			
		S.S.	M.S.	P pr	Exp. %	S.S.	M.S.	P pr	Exp. %
Total	119	2704.7	22.7			3724	31.3		
Treatments (G,E,GEI)	11	2053	186.6	<0.001	75.9	2581	234.7	<0.001	69.3
Genotypes (G)	3	461.2	153.7	<0.001	17.1	697	232.4	<0.001	18.7
Environment (E)	2	1343.3	671.6	<0.001	49.7	1554	777.2	<0.001	41.7
Replicate (E)	12	50.7	4.2	0.7716	1.9	148	12.4	0.2976	4.0
Interaction (GxE)	6	248.6	41.4	<0.001	9.2	330	55	<0.001	8.9
IPCA1	4	245	61.3	<0.001	9.1	324	81	<0.001	8.7
IPCA2	2	3.6	1.8	0.7528	0.1	6	2.9	0.7562	0.2
IPCA Residuals	0	0				0			
Error	96	601	6.3			994	10.4		

Note: D.F = degree of freedom; SS = sum of Square; MS = mean of square; Exp. = Explained variation (%).

AMMI stability value and yield stability index for identifying genotype yield stability

The mean performance of the varieties for total tuber yield across the environments ranged from $15.88t\ ha^{-1}$ to $22.23t\ ha^{-1}$ and marketable yield ranged from $9.34t\ ha^{-1}$ to $14.3t\ ha^{-1}$ with considerable yield differences in each environment shown in Table 4 and 5 respectively. The best genotype that performs high marketable and total yield across all environments was Sequoia compared to the yields of the other three genotypes. This confirms the farmers' suggestion on the yield performance of Sequoia compared to NARI released genotypes including E2 and E24 (Anton *et al.*, 2020).

The analysis using AMMI stability value (ASV) indicated that Kumdi had a lower ASV value and this revealed that this genotype was ranked first and is relatively more stable than the other genotypes (Table 4 and 5). This is also visualized in the AMMI biplot of IPCA1 scores shown in Figure 2. Kumdi is laying very close to the PC1 score line which indicates that its yield is more stable across all environments. Stability is not the only parameters for the selection of high yielding genotypes as the most stable genotypes would not necessarily give

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the best yield performance (Lule *et al.*, 2014). The yield stability index (YSI) revealed the genotype with both high yielding and more stable (Miheretu, 2014 and Verma *et al.*, 2016). As such, the YSI revealed that Sequoia is the best genotype integrating both stability and tuber yield performance followed by Kumdi then E2 and E24 for marketable and total tuber yield (Table 4 and 5). This is also confirmed visually in the AMMI biplot of PC1 score in Figure 2.

Table 4: Mean total yield (t ha⁻¹) of genotypes and environment by AMMI model, IPCA scores, AMMI stability value (ASV) and yield stability index (YSI) and rankings.

Genotype (G)	Environment			G mean	IPCA1 Score	IPCA2 score	ASV	YSI	Rank ASV	Rank YSI
	Aiyura	Pepik	Yawar							
Kumdi	19.50	16.46	11.67	15.88	0.07	-0.74	4.03	5	1	4
E2	21.02	20.69	10.13	17.28	-1.61	0.15	89.58	6	3	3
E24	22.12	14.60	15.22	17.31	1.75	0.21	97.52	6	4	2
Sequoia	26.56	23.03	17.10	22.23	-0.21	0.38	11.64	3	2	1
E Mean	22.3	18.7	13.53							

Table 5: Mean marketable yield (t ha⁻¹) of genotypes and environment by AMMI model, IPCA scores, AMMI stability value (ASV) and yield stability index (YSI) and rankings.

Genotype (G)	Environment (E)			G mean	IPCA1 Score	IPCA2 score	ASV	YSI	Rank ASV	Rank YSI
	Aiyura	Pepik	Yawar							
Kumdi	12.43	10.5	5.08	9.34	0.04	0.60	2.49	5	1	4
E2	13.63	12.9	4.42	10.32	-0.93	0.06	63.65	5	3	2
E24	13.72	7.95	8.02	9.89	1.80	-0.21	123.99	7	4	3
Sequoia	17.93	16.73	8.25	14.3	-0.91	-0.44	62.76	3	2	1
E Mean	14.43	12.02	6.44							

Figure 2: AMMI biplot of IPCA1 scores against marketable and total tuber yield for the genotypes across three environments.

Fresh boiled and fried chips consumer preferences

Freshly boiled taste differences of potato are affected by the different levels of sugar and dry matter content in the tubers (Pevicharova, 2015; Lisinska *et al.*, 2009). The fresh boiled tuber flesh colour, aroma, taste and overall acceptance parameters of the four potato varieties were highly ($P < 0.05$) preferred by more than 50% of the test panel compared to moderately like and dislike preferences (Table 6). Kumdi was strongly liked (<75%)

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by the test panel while E24 was liked the least (<47%) for all boiled tuber testing parameters. The flesh colour, taste and overall acceptance of the boiled tuber for Kumdi were strongly preferred compared to other varieties. Overall, all varieties are acceptable to consumers where there is no strong dislike (<20%) for any of them. This result is similar to the results generated from the Kabwum potato variety evaluation trial conducted by Anton and Sitango (unpublished). They stated that the freshly boiled tubers for Kumdi were mostly preferred by the test panel followed by E2 and E24. The freshly boiled taste differences of potato were affected by the different levels of sugar and dry matter content in the tubers (Pevicharova, 2015; Lisinska et al., 2009).

Like the freshly boiled tuber preferences, the fried chips test parameters for all varieties were strongly liked by the test population and least preferred the moderately like and dislike preferences (Table 7). Between 45 – 60% of the consumer liked all the fried chips test parameters and less than 25% moderately like and disliked the fried chip's parameters assessed. The flesh colour and aroma of Kumdi was highly preferred and also the taste and overall acceptance of the test qualities were strongly preferred after Sequoia. E24 was least liked when compared with other varieties but it was strongly liked compared to dislike preferences. Generally, there were no strong disliked preferences for all varieties and the test population well-liked the fried chips test quality parameters for all varieties.

Table 6: Boiled tuber quality preferences (%) of four potato varieties evaluated against three agro-ecological sites in the highlands.

Cultivar	Flesh color			Aroma			Taste			Overall acceptance		
	Dislike	¹ Mode.	like	Dislike	Mode	like	Dislike	Mode	like	Dislike	Mode	like
Kumdi	13	19	68	25	31	44	13	12	75	13	16	71
E2	13	25	62	13	41	46	13	28	59	12	25	63
E24	25	31	44	25	31	44	34	22	44	28	25	47
Sequoia	13	19	68	13	40	47	16	25	59	13	19	68
Mean	16	23	61	19	36	45	19	22	59	16	21	63
LSD	10			12			6			14		
CV (%)	27			33			18			40		
F (P<0.05)	*			*			*			*		

Note: ¹Mode. = Moderate like; * = Significant at P<0.05

Table 7: Fried chips quality preferences (%) of four potato varieties evaluated against three agro-ecological sites in the highlands.

Variety	Flesh color			Aroma			Taste			Overall acceptance		
	Dislike	¹ Mode.	like	Dislike	Mode	like	Dislike	Mode	like	Dislike	Mode	like
Kumdi	13	28	59	12	38	50	9	29	63	6	38	56
E2	13	31	56	32	42	46	6	46	48	6	41	53
E24	22	25	53	12	36	32	18	34	48	19	31	50
Sequoia	13	34	53	14	43	44	3	28	69	13	25	65
Mean	15	29	56	18	40	42	9	35	56	11	33	56
LSD	12			12			15			15		
CV	31			32			41			41		
F (P<0.05)	*			*			*			*		

Note: ¹Mode. = Moderate like; * = Significant at (P<0.05)

Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA)

Kumdi had the highest net benefit or profit margin followed by E24, Sequoia and E2 for the Yawar site (Table 8 and Annex 1). However, E2 and E24 had the highest profit for Jiwaka and Aiyura respectively followed by Sequoia and Kundi (Table 8). The gross field benefit was calculated from marketable and seed field benefits. The value of the gross field benefits depends on the yield performance of each variety. Generally, Aiyura had

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the highest field benefits followed by Pepik and Yawar resulted in a high-profit margin value respectively (Table 8). Sequoia had the highest field benefits for Yawar and Pepik and E24 had the highest field benefit for Aiyura. As expected, Sequoia also had the highest variable cost (K22,595.01 ha⁻¹) due to the cost of fungicide and its application compared to the variable cost of other varieties without fungicide application (K19,733.01 ha⁻¹) (Annex 1). Almost 13% of the variable cost of Sequoia was from the management of PLB disease infestation (Minemba and Kerru, 2014; Anton and Ovah unpublished). Thus, Kumdi had the highest profit margin (K12,965.99 ha⁻¹) followed by E24 (K11,550.49 ha⁻¹) for Yawar while E2 had the highest profit margin (K25,068.99) followed by E24 (K24,218.74) for Pepik and E24 had the highest profit margin (K40,582.49) followed by E2 (K36,516.49) for Aiyura site (Table 8). Anton and Ovah (unpublished) stated in their potato economic analysis report of a trial conducted at Tambul that Kumdi had the highest profit margin which is confirmed in this study.

Table 8: Summary economic analysis of four potato varieties evaluated at different agro-environments (Details analysis for Yawar are presented as sample in Annex 1)

YAWAR				
Items	Kumdi	E2	E24	Sequoia Sprayed
Gross field benefits (K ha ⁻¹)	32,699.00	30,903.50	31,283.50	34,033.75
Total Variable Costs (K ha ⁻¹)	19,733.01	19,733.01	19,733.01	22,595.01
Net benefits/Profit (K ha⁻¹)	12,965.99	11,170.49	11,550.49	11,438.74
PEPIK				
Gross field benefits (K ha ⁻¹)	34,907.75	44,802.00	43,951.75	45,566.75
Total Variable Costs (K ha ⁻¹)	19,733.01	19,733.01	19,733.01	22,595.01
Net benefits/Profit (K ha⁻¹)	15,174.74	25,068.99	24,218.74	22,971.74
AIYURA				
Gross field benefits (K ha ⁻¹)	44,835.25	56,249.50	60,315.50	56,729.25
Total Variable Costs (K ha ⁻¹)	19,733.01	19,733.01	19,733.01	22,595.01
Net benefits/Profit (K ha⁻¹)	25,102.24	36,516.49	40,582.49	34,134.24

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Landrace Kumdi potato cultivar evaluated across three environments against the PLB resistant varieties E2 and E24 showed a high level of resistance (95 – 100%) to PLB pathogen, unlike Sequoia which is highly susceptible. The ANOVA results indicated that the environments are diverse and the studied cultivars rank differently for their yield traits when grown at different locations. Generally, yields of Kumdi were highly stable across all environments followed by Sequoia whereas E2 and E24 adapted well in the high altitude environment. Thus, this suggests that Kumdi and Sequoia can be grown in a wider range of altitudes and temperatures across similar agro-ecological zones in PNG. In addition, the freshly boiled and fried chips consumer preferences for these two varieties with two other CIP varieties were highly preferred by the test population and can be recommended. All potato varieties evaluated including the landrace cultivar Kumdi are recommended to cultivate across similar environments with good management practices to generate a profit margin of 50 to 150%.

Kumdi had genetic traits that resisted 95 – 100% PLB fungus infestation and showed wide stability across tested environments, acceptable profit margin and highly preferred boiled and fried chips consumer preferences. Therefore, the local landrace cultivar can be promoted for further research using clean planting materials and also for the production of elite seeds through formal seeds system and disseminate to farmers to support food security and cash income.

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REFERENCE

- i. Anton, J., Roberts, A., Sitango, K., Amben, S. and Ahizo, J. (2018). *Management Practices for the Recovery for Irish Potato after Frost Incidence in the High Altitude of PNG*. Unigor Ltd printing and publication, PNG.
- ii. Anton, J., Sitango, K., & Roberts, A. (2020). *Stem Height and Yield Response of Four Potato Varieties to Planting Density and Fertilizer in Tambul, Western Highlands Province, Papua New Guinea*. *International Journal of Horticultural Science*, 6(1), 092-098.
- iii. Baird, D., Murray, D., Payne, R., & Soutar, D. (2019). *Introduction to Genstat for windows (20th Edition)* VSN International LTD. VSN International LTD, 2 Amberside, Wood Lane, UK.
- iv. Bonierbale, M. (2007). *Procedures for standard evaluation trials of advanced potato clones. An international cooperator's guide*. International Potato Center.
- v. Bourke, R., Allen, M., & Salisbury, J. (2001). *Food Security for Papua New Guinea: Proceedings of the Papua New Guinea Food and Nutrition 2000 Conference, PNG University of Technology, Lae, 26-30 June 2000 (Issue 99)*. ACIAR.
- vi. Byarugaba, A. A., Benon, M., Tibanyedera, D., & Barekye, A. (2018). *Genotype by environment interaction (GxE) as a measure of yield stability of Dutch potato varieties in Uganda*. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 13(17), 890-896.
- vii. FAO (2009). *The State of Food and Agriculture 2009*. Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations, Rome, Italy. ISBN: 9789251062159.
- viii. Forbes, G. (2012). *Using host resistance to manage potato late blight with particular reference to developing countries*. *Potato Research*, 55(3-4), 205-216.
- ix. FPDA Annual Report (2013) *Fresh Produce Development Agency, Goroka, Eastern Highlands Province, Papua New Guinea*.
- x. Funga, A., Tadesse M., Eshete M., Fikre, A., Korbu, L., Girma N., Bekele, D., Mohamed, R. and Bishaw, Z. (2017). *Genotype by environment interaction on yield stability of desi type chickpea at major chickpea production areas of Ethiopia*. *Australia Journal of Crop Science*, 11 (02) 212-219.
- xi. Gauch, H., & Zobel, R. (1996). *AMMI analysis in yield trials*. KANG, MS, GAUCH, HG (Ed) *Genotype by environment interaction*.
- xii. Kerru, B. A. and Akanda, S. (2011). *Evaluation of CIP potato breeding lines for Late Blight resistance and yield at Tambul in the Highlands of Papua New Guinea*. *Niugini Agrisaiens*. Volume 3, 30-36, 2011.
- xiii. Kromannet, P., Miethbauer, T., Ortiz, O., & Forbes, G. A. (2014). *Review of potato biotic constraints and experiences with integrated pest management interventions*. In *Integrated pest management* (pp. 245-268). Springer.
- xiv. Lisinska, G., Peksa, A., Kita, A., Rytel, E. and Czopek, (2009). *The Quality of Potato for Processing and Consumption*. Global Science Book, Poland.
- xv. Lule, D., Tesfaye K. and Mengistu G. (2014). *Genotype by environment interaction and grain yield stability analysis for advanced Triticale Genotypes in Western Oromia, Ethiopia*. *College of Natural Sciences, Addis Ababa University*. 37 (1), 63-68.

February 28, 2022

- xvi. Miheretu, F. (2014). *Genotype and Environment Interaction and Marketable Tuber Yield Stability of Potato (Solanumtuberosum L) Genotypes Grown in Bale Highlands, Southeastern Ethiopia. Advance Crop Science and Technology. 2(1) 2329-8863.*
- xvii. Minemba, D. and Kerru, A. (2014). *Management of Potato Late Blight Disease in Papua New Guinea. Final Project Report. Project no. CD/2003/029.*
- xviii. Ngeve, J. (1993). *Regression analysis of genotype x environment interaction in sweet potato. Euphytica, 71(3), 231–238.*
- xix. Olivoto, T., & Lúcio, A. D. (2020). *metan: An R package for multi-environment trial analysis. Methods in Ecology and Evolution.*
- xx. Pevicharova, G. (2015). *Correlation between Sensory Traits of Boiled Potato. Bulgarina Journal of Agriculture Science, 21 (No 4) 877-881. Agriculture Academy.*
- xxi. Rani, A., Singh, R., Kumar, P., and Shukla, G. (2017). *PROS and CONS OF FUNGICIDES: AN OVERVIEW. International Journal of Engineering Science and Research Technology. 6(1), 2277-9655.*
- xxii. Sawanga, B. (1991). *Field Pocket Book on Potato, Pocket Book No. 4. Department of Agriculture and Livestock, Port Moresby.*
- xxiii. Tjosvold, S. A. (2018). *Disease Triangle: Fundamental Concept for Disease Management. UC ARN Blogs.*
- xxiv. Vera, B., Deros M., Kawale, G., Ramakrishna A., Anton, J., Sitango, K. and Guaf, E. (2018). *Study of Genotype x Environment Interaction for Sweet Potato Tuber Yield and Related Traits in Papua New Guinea. International Journal of Crop Breeding. 5(1), 308-323.*
- xxv. Verma, R.P.S., Kharab, A. S., Singh, J., Kumar, V., Sharma, I. and Verma, A. (2016). *AMMI model to analysis GxE for dual purpose barley in multi-environmental trials. Agriculture Research Communication Center. 36 (1) 9-16.*
- xxvi. Zadoks, J. C., & Schein, R. D. (1979). *Epidemiology and plant disease management. Epidemiology and Plant Disease Management.*
- xxvii. Zali H., Farshadfar E., Sabaghpour S. H. and Karimizadeh R. 2012. *Evaluation of genotype × environment interaction in chickpea using measures of stability from AMMI model. Ann. Biol. Res., 3: 3126-3136*

Annex 1: Economic analysis of four potato varieties evaluated at Yawar

Items	Kumdi	E2	E24	Sequoia Sprayed
Average yield (t ha ⁻¹)	5.08	4.42	8.02	8.25
Average mark ¹ . yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	5080.00	4420.00	8020.00	8250.00
Adjusted mark. Yield (-5%)	4826	4199	7619	7837.5
Field benefits² (K ha⁻¹)	7,239.00	6,298.50	11,428.50	11,756.25
Average seed yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	5360.00	5180.00	4180.00	4690.00
Adjusted seed yield (-5%)	5092.00	4921.00	3971.00	4455.50
Field benefits³ (K ha⁻¹)	25,460.00	24,605.00	19,855.00	22,277.50
Gross field benefits (K ha⁻¹)	32,699.00	30,903.50	31,283.50	34,033.75
Variable Costs				
Plant population density (K ha ⁻¹)	10,359.12	10,359.12	10,359.12	10,359.12
Fertilizer application rate (K ha ⁻¹)	4,500.00	4,500.00	4,500.00	4,500.00
Fertilizer transport (K ha ⁻¹)	67.00	67.00	67.00	67.00
Karate (K ha ⁻¹)	40.00	40.00	40.00	40.00
Eko (K ha ⁻¹)	0.00	0.00	0.00	1,512.00

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Land preparation (K ha ⁻¹)	484.85	484.85	484.85	484.85
Planting (K ha ⁻¹)	301.72	301.72	301.72	301.72
Hilling & weeding (K ha ⁻¹)	281.00	281.00	281.00	281.00
Spray karate (K ha ⁻¹)	50.00	50.00	50.00	50.00
Spray Eko (K ha ⁻¹)	0.00	0.00	0.00	1,350.00
Harvesting (K ha ⁻¹)	203.49	203.49	203.49	203.49
25 kg net bags – est'd cost	2,770.83	2,770.83	2,770.83	2,770.83
Trans. to roadside (K ha ⁻¹)	675.00	675.00	675.00	675.00
Total Variable Costs (K ha⁻¹)	19,733.01	19,733.01	19,733.01	22,595.01
Net benefits/Profit (K ha⁻¹)	12,965.99	11,170.49	11,550.49	11,438.74

Note: ¹ = Marketable; ² = marketable benefits; ³ = seed benefi